

DEVELOPING THE CREATIVITY COMPETENCE OF LISTENERS IN PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT COURSES (BASED ON GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS)

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Abstract. *In this article due to the methodical rational organization of the pedagogical process, the correct determination of the forms of educational or educational activities, the ability to choose methods and tools in accordance with the purpose, to be able to use them effectively and successfully, to search for, collect, and sort the necessary information in the information environment, processing and using them effectively requires great skill from today's teacher. One of the important practical tasks is to develop the competence of students to conduct interactive lessons in the training system, as in all areas of education. The article describes the opinions about this.*

Keywords: *competence, lesson, interactive, didactic, information acquisition, cooperation, independent observation, problem-based learning, project-based learning, creative learning, heuristic learning.*

Introduction. Innovative technology, which is one of the factors ensuring the quality and efficiency of education, new pedagogical technology, including the introduction of interactive education into the educational process, is becoming the necessity of the day. The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov, said, "...in our lives, the period of achieving a positive "explosion effect", i.e., a strong effect of the educational model continues.

In our schools, a new generation of textbooks, modernized programs, passing experiments and tests, are being improved at the level of current requirements, and the material base of schools is being strengthened.

Construction of new schools, reconstruction, current and major repairs, provision of modern equipment, technical means, computerization, social protection of students and teachers, material and moral stimulation are carried out on the basis of programs and plans. No matter how much the material base of schools is developed, no matter how textbooks, programs, and standards are improved, giving the student thorough and in-depth knowledge, teaching him to think freely and creatively, the professional skills and knowledge of the teacher, the extent to which he has mastered modern lessons, advanced technologies, and the ability to organize interactive lessons today's graduate will stay connected.

In general, can today's pedagogue organize a lesson in new conditions, using new methods?

The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov, drew attention to the fact that attracting qualified teachers to the primary education system is one of the measures aimed at ensuring the quality and efficiency of education at this stage, and emphasized the following: simple logic requires that coaches be locked up.

This, in turn, requires humanizing, liberalizing, democratizing, child-friendly, cooperation and co-creative organization of the educational process is doing. In short, the student should be at the center of the learning process. The educational process is required to be student-oriented and oriented. Individualized education serves as a driving force for the organization of the student's educational work, realizing interest, desire, demand, and wishes. That is, what should be understood by the individual approach to the educational process?

Individual approach in the educational process:

- increasing student activity;
- teaching the student to think independently;
- organization of student's creative thinking;
- ensuring the student's independence and freedom;
- working on the basis of students' interests (motivation);
- using the student's capabilities;
- referral to additional, extracurricular education through their interests;
- refers to self-development, education.

Based on the development of the above-mentioned individual characteristics, the student's independent learning skills and qualifications are formed. A high level of independent learning and mastering skills is measured by competence (ability).

Competence (lat. *competere* – to be capable, to be worthy) is a person's awareness of a certain field, the level of knowledge of this field, knowledge, skills, competence, a set of views, the value and qualities of a person, the ability to demonstrate competence or influence.

According to this definition, the stages of formation of the professional competence of a training trainee should be as follows:

1. Self-analysis and awareness of essentials.
2. Planning of self-development, setting goals and tasks.
3. Self-expression and correction of shortcomings.

In-service trainees absorb knowledge from a 144-hour course load over four weeks of study, sharing experiences while gaining new skills and competencies in academic subjects. As a result, a specialist with professional competence:

1. consistently enriches his knowledge;
2. learns new information;
3. deeply understands the requirements of the era;
4. seeks new knowledge;
5. process them and use them effectively in their practical work. In this case, the level of didactic competence develops.

The level of didactic competence consists of the following:

- creating a learning environment;
- plan to cover the content of the topic;
- management of the educational process;
- evaluation of students' achievements and development;
- providing motivation and support to students;
- understanding and development of students' knowledge.

Based on N.Muslimov's opinion about professional and didactic competence, we present the following points. It is no secret that reforming the educational process begins with reforming the lesson. Where to start reforming the lesson? Lesson:

- to have a responsible attitude to the lesson;
- introducing a new approach to the lesson;
- individual approach to the student in the lesson;
- organization of the lesson based on student's activity, partner and co-creativity;
- it is necessary to start with the use of interactive, innovative, advanced technologies.

What is an interactive method and what does it mean? Interactive methods implement the learning process in the interaction and interaction of students. Interactive is derived from the English word "interast", which means inter - mutual, ast - action, influence, activity.

The lessons organized on the basis of interactivity in the training system require an andragogic approach from the listeners, and are directed to the development of the skills and abilities of free thinking and active decision-making, based on life experience in correctly presenting one's own experience, finding solutions to problems in groups, working in cooperation, and expressing one's thoughts in writing. . Working in interactive methods does not mean abandoning traditional methods, but it means being able to organize the solution of the lesson content in mutual activity, cooperation and co-creation.

There are the following methods of interactive education:

- problem education;
- project education;
- education through the game;
- creative education;
- heuristic education;
- ICT education.

Interactivity is the activity of two people, that is, the learning process takes place in the form of a mutual conversation, in the form of a dialogue (computer communication) or on the basis of teacher-student interactions.

Based on my personal experience, I recommend the following three directions for developing the level of competence of trainees:

Direction I. To guide the listeners by teaching more about psychology, pedagogy, methodology, informatics, educational model in the process of pedagogical practice, the essence of interactive education and the mechanism of its implementation.

Direction II. Formation of small creative groups, consisting of 5-6 listeners in each group, teaching and mastering interactive education. After studying each method of interactive educational methods, conduct seminars-trainings, roundtable discussions, discussions based on a special schedule. Establishing a system of continuous training and education of listeners.

Direction III. To enable students to conduct scientific pedagogical research based on their personal programs. Search, collect, create a bank of scientific-methodical literature and daily periodical press materials, advanced pedagogical experiences, Internet materials, and use them during pedagogical activity.

Conclusion. In short, the main goal of the interactive method is to create an environment for active, free, creative thinking of the listener by creating the most favorable environment and

situation for the learning process. It means ensuring the quality and efficiency of education by demonstrating the intellectual potential of the student and his internal capabilities.

Interactive lessons are held in such a way that not a single student is left out, that is, they have the opportunity to openly express their opinions on what they have heard, read, seen and known. A process of exchange of mutual knowledge, ideas, thoughts takes place. This ensures sincerity in the course of the lesson, the desire to learn, interest increases, mutual support and friendly relations are formed.

By organizing interactive lessons, students learn to work individually, in pairs, and in small groups. In this case, research-based plans, role-playing games, pre-planning, algorithmization, modularization, working with textbooks, working with various documents, working with information sources, and creative works can be used in the organized training.

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